

Blunt Trauma Abdomen with Splenic Injury in a Patient with Situs Inversus: A Case Report

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Received: 25-07-2024 / Revised: 23-08-2024 / Accepted: 26-09-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Situs inversus is a rare condition characterized by the mirror-image reversal of the anatomical arrangement of visceral organs. It may be associated with dextrocardia (totalis) or levocardia (incomplete) and is inherited in an autosomal recessive manner. This condition can be linked to congenital heart diseases, ciliary dysfunction, and complications related to anaesthesia. Splenic injury in a patient with situs inversus following blunt abdominal trauma is extremely rare. In cases of high-grade injuries, an emergency splenectomy is typically required, although Tran's catheter arterial embolization may be attempted in paediatric patients if extravasation is observed. Prophylactic appendectomy may also be considered in such cases. Due to the rarity of this condition, limited information is available regarding postoperative complications, as only a few case reports have been documented. This case report presents a 30-year-old female who was admitted to the emergency department with a history of blunt abdominal trauma, hypotension, and vomiting. A contrast-enhanced CT scan of the abdomen revealed situs inversus totalis with a grade 3 splenic injury, for which an exploratory laparotomy and emergency splenectomy were performed. This is an exceptionally rare case, with fewer than five similar cases reported in the literature to date. Given the potential for postoperative complications related to ciliary dysfunction, anaesthesia, and congenital heart defects, a thorough preoperative evaluation is essential to minimize the risk of such complications.

Keywords: Situs inversus, Splenectomy, Dextrocardia, Appendicectomy.

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Introduction

Situs inversus is a rare congenital condition characterized by the transposition of major organs to the opposite side of the body, resulting in a complete mirror image of their normal anatomical arrangement. The prevalence of situs inversus varies across populations but occurs in less than 1 in 10,000 individuals. [1] There are two types of situs inversus: situs inversus totalis, also known as situs inversus with dextrocardia, where the heart is positioned on the right side of the thorax, [2] and situs inversus incomplete, also known as situs inversus with levocardia, which is much rarer (affecting 1 in 22,000 individuals), where the heart remains on the left side of the thorax. [3]

The mirror-image positioning of the major visceral organs in these patients can lead to atypical symptom presentation and unusual imaging findings, which complicates diagnosis. Surgeons must be aware of the "flipped" orientation of the

organs and adapt their surgical approach accordingly. There may be an association between situs inversus and conditions such as congenital heart disease and primary ciliary dyskinesia. [4,5]

We report the case of a 30-year-old female with situs inversus totalis who sustained blunt abdominal trauma, resulting in a grade III spleen injury accompanied by an inflamed appendix. The management of acute abdomen in such cases is challenging due to the altered anatomy and the increased risk of associated congenital heart conditions.

Case report

A 30-year-old female was admitted to the emergency department of Gandhi Hospital, Secunderabad, on February 15, 2023, presenting with acute abdominal symptoms following blunt trauma. She had a history of loss of consciousness

for 45 minutes and one episode of vomiting. The patient had a known allergy to paracetamol. On examination, her Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) score was 15/15, her blood pressure was 90/50 mmHg, and her pulse was 106 bpm. She also had a congenital absence of the second and fourth fingers on her left hand, and abrasions were noted on the right side of her abdomen. Abdominal examination revealed diffuse tenderness and guarding. A provisional diagnosis of peritonitis was made.

A chest X-ray supported the clinical findings, showing the cardiac shadow on the right side (Fig. 1). An ultrasound (USG) of the abdomen revealed situs inversus, mild hemoperitoneum, altered splenic echotexture, and an ectopic pelvic kidney. A contrast-enhanced CT (CECT) of the abdomen confirmed a grade 3 splenic injury, while a CT scan of the brain was normal. An emergency exploratory laparotomy was performed. Intraoperatively, 500 ml of hemoperitoneum was found. The liver was

located on the left side of the abdomen along with the gallbladder (Fig. 2), and the spleen, on the right side, had sustained a grade 3 injury (Fig. 3). Situs inversus totalis was confirmed, with the cecum and appendix located on the left side. Additionally, a 6 cm inflamed appendix (Fig. 4) was found in the left iliac fossa. Due to the severity of the splenic injury, a splenectomy was performed. An appendectomy was also conducted to prevent future diagnostic confusion in case of left iliac fossa pain.

Postoperatively, the patient was closely monitored in the ICU on oxygen support. She developed bilateral lung crepitations and was placed on non-invasive ventilation (NIV), but by the end of postoperative day 0, she required intubation due to inadequate oxygen saturation. Despite aggressive management, the patient rapidly deteriorated, developing acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS) (Fig. 5) and, unfortunately, passed away on postoperative day 2.

Figure 1: Chest X-ray showing situs inversus with dextrocardia

Figure 2: Left hypochondrium showing liver and gallbladder

Figure 3: Grade 3 splenic injury

Figure 4: Inflamed and dilated appendix removed

Figure 5: Postoperative day 3 chest X-ray showing diffuse lung involvement and ARDS

Discussion

The term "situs inversus," derived from Latin meaning "inverted position of the internal organs," was first introduced by Scottish physician Matthew Baillie in 1787. In contrast to situs solitus, which refers to the normal positioning of internal organs, situs inversus describes the mirror image of this arrangement, where major thoracic and abdominal viscera are reversed. Specifically, the stomach and spleen are located on the right, and the hepatobiliary system is on the left. The terms levocardia and dextrocardia indicate the direction of the cardiac apex. Situs inversus with dextrocardia is also called situs inversus totalis because both the cardiac position and the arrangement of atrial chambers and abdominal organs mirror normal anatomy. [6]

Situs inversus is typically an autosomal recessive genetic condition, though it can also be X-linked. [7] Individuals with situs inversus totalis have a 5–10% prevalence of congenital heart disease, with common abnormalities including transposition of the great vessels, atrial septal defects, ventricular septal defects, absent coronary sinus, double-outlet right ventricle, total anomalous pulmonary venous return, and pulmonary valve stenosis, either singly or in combination. Congenitally corrected transposition of the great arteries, in which the right atrium drains into the left ventricle and further into the pulmonary artery and vice versa, can occur in individuals with situs inversus and dextrocardia, who may remain asymptomatic until adulthood.

Situs inversus totalis may also be associated with primary ciliary dyskinesia, known as Kartagener syndrome, which may or may not involve bronchiectasis, depending on the diagnostic criteria. [8] Diagnosis of this condition requires tests such as low exhaled nasal nitric oxide measurement, the saccharin test, ciliary beat pattern and frequency analysis, and electron microscopy to confirm the ultrastructural ciliary defect. Airway ciliary dysfunction could predispose patients with situs inversus to increased vulnerability to postoperative complications. Primary ciliary dyskinesia is present in 25% of individuals with situs inversus totalis, raising the likelihood of developing respiratory complications. [9] Anesthetic management in these patients can be complicated due to the high incidence of congenital heart defects. The presence of situs inversus complicates diagnosis and management due to altered anatomy. In our extensive review of the literature, we found fewer than five cases of splenic injury following blunt abdominal trauma in patients with situs inversus. One case involved a child managed with trans catheter arterial embolization, while in the other three cases, splenectomy was performed. [10-12] In our case, the respiratory failure that developed postoperatively may have

been due to an underlying congenital cardiac defect, primary ciliary dyskinesia, anesthetic complications, or a combination of these factors. However, we were unable to definitively identify the cause due to the limitations of diagnostic facilities at our center.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this case of a 30-year-old female with situs inversus totalis who sustained a grade III splenic injury following blunt abdominal trauma highlights the complexities of managing acute abdominal conditions in the presence of altered anatomy. The coexistence of an inflamed appendix added to the diagnostic and therapeutic challenges. The altered anatomical positions of the viscera, along with the potential for underlying congenital cardiac and respiratory conditions, such as primary ciliary dyskinesia, increased the patient's risk of postoperative complications.

Despite timely surgical intervention with a splenectomy and appendectomy, the patient succumbed to acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS) two days postoperatively. Furthermore, it reinforces the importance of comprehensive perioperative management in such rare and anatomically challenging cases, where underlying conditions may not be readily identifiable.

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